

The Effects of Service Quality Perceptions of Turkish Cruise Tourists on Their Behavioral Intentions and Satisfaction

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Abstract

The main aim of this study was to find out the effects of the service quality perceptions of Turkish cruise tourists on their general levels of behavioral intentions and satisfaction. For this goal, a questionnaire was used to collect data from cruise ship tourists in this paper. The questionnaires were implemented on 206 Turkish cruise tourists. Results showed that the perceived components of service quality have remarkable effect on behavioral intentions and general satisfaction levels of tourists.

Keywords: *behavioral intentions, service quality, Turkish cruise tourists, satisfaction*

Introduction

In the period from past to present, one of the most important commercial transport vehicles have been vessels (Müller, 1990). Especially after the geographical discoveries, world trade volume has increased and, accordingly, people's level of welfare began to rise, resulting in a gradual increase in the trend among especially high income groups in economically advanced countries for performing sea travels like maritime explorers did in the past, along with the advancements in technology. Black Ball, the world's first overseas passenger transport company, booked regular voyages from the US to destinations in the U.K., in 1889. Even the disastrous sinking of Titanic could not lessen the interest in people for sea travel (Güzel, 2006). The developments taking place in the cruise tourism industry, particularly during the period following the Second World War at both supply and demand sides of the business delivered notable economic growth in maritime transport of passengers (Güzel, 2006) and eventually, cruise tourism revived as an alternate method of touring, rather than adding on to the existing stock of modalities of passenger transport, in the second half of 20th century (Johnson, 2002). Such progress achieved by the cruise travel industry both in itself and in cooperation with other sectors of industrial engagement with which it interacts started to bring significant contributions not only to the enterprises, but also to the tourism economies of countries, as well. The industry generated revenues totaling to US\$ 30 billion for the United States Government, in 2004 (Güzel, 2006). Consequently, as a look into the present day would expressly reveal, cruise ship operation continues to be a major area of tourism today, just as in the past and the amount of interest shown by enterprises, countries and people on it grows daily (Gorken, 2011). At this end, it is essential to correctly analyze and put forth the variety of reasons that underlie purchasing or opposite

behaviors, insofar as grabbing a slice from this cake and persuading people to stay on a cruise ship for the entire duration of their holidays poses importance. So, it is critical for companies, tour operators and travel agents involved in cruise tourism business to correctly assess and identify the various demands and requirements, service perceptions and behavioral intentions of cruise tourists, in order to convince their customers to sign up for a journey/holiday on a cruise ship.

This research was conducted to specify the effects of the service quality perceptions of Turkish cruise tourists on their behavioral intentions and general levels of satisfaction. At first, the research makes clarifications about cruise tourism, perceived quality of service and its measurement, as well as on behavioral intentions and then performs an analysis/assessment to state the service quality that perceived by Turkish cruise tourists under the section titled findings and conducts a review and analysis of the factors involved therein, on intentions for repeated preference, as well as for recommending the services offered in this category.

Turkey is a destination quite rich of resources for cruise tourism with 8333 kilometers long coastal line and shore structures as well as diverse historical and cultural assets and a country with people constantly growing interest on cruise tourism, during the recent years. During the last couple of years, the travel organizations operating in Turkey have started to respond to the emerging demand for this particular line of business, by acquiring cruise ships either by way of purchasing or leasing (<http://www.etstur.com/Cruise-Gemi-Turlari>; Interview with Ms. Ipek Sapmaz, Supervisor of Maritime Tourism in Turkish Chamber of Maritime Commerce, May 2012). MSC Cruise Enterprise declared a quota for Turkish passengers to embark on

their ships, in view of the increasing demand. It is now reported that this quota, which was reserved exclusively for travelers of Turkish origin, has been filled at 100% and is expected to increase further, in the upcoming times (Interview with Fatih Sarioglu, Responsible of MSC Turkey, May 2012). In light of these updates, it becomes apparent that, with the potential, they exhibit; Turkish cruise tourists will turn out to be an important target group for the enterprises, and should therefore be assessed and analyzed perfectly.

Literature Review

Today, the term cruise defines a ship, that attains certain standards in terms of size and comfort, which is used for conducting holiday trips with shore-side overnight accommodation (Çimenoglu, 2011). In its simplest form, the term cruise tourism can be defined as “a travel performed on sea, by stopping at various seaport/harbor destinations, for pleasure” (Dowling, 2006, 3–17). According to Israel and Miller (1999), cruise tourism reflects accommodation in a large hotel facility and has pretty much the same functions, for numerous aspects. However, the travelers on a cruise ship are frequently defined as daily guests and tourists. The World Tourism Organization, on the other hand, describes them as “guests boarding and leaving on the same day” (WTO, 1992). In cruise tourism, there are activities comprised of port visits, sightseeing tours and shopping. The ports at which cruise ships anchor and services provided to travelers at these ports are the areas in which host countries invest, by weight (Israel and Miller, 1999).

However, the high costs of cruise ships, and accordingly high levels retained for pricing of the service, in combination with visa requirements for countries entered are among the most prominent barriers against increasingly more tourists purchasing this service. According to Park (2006), the client base restricted to a certain target group of travelers who make preference over cruise tourism is a factor that drives competition harsher, in this industry. The cruise enterprises, on the other hand, lay impetus on grabbing share in the existing market, instead of for expanding it (Park, 2006). However, the fast increasing numbers of cruise ships can only hold 4000 to 4500 tourists, in addition to an 8% average annual growth in cruise tourism industry since 1980 till the present day (Teyeand Leclerc, 1998; Toh, Rivers and Ling, 2005; Petrick, Li, and Park, 2007; Lobo, 2008). By doing so, the enterprises gain trust and preference of tourists in relatively lower income groups who have not yet purchased any cruise service until today by lowering the per capita head passenger costs, and making the sector and their alternative service offering more appealing for these potential clients with the additional

opportunities they provide (Industry Report of the Turkish Chamber of Maritime Commerce, 2010). Furthermore, the cruise tourism’s focusing solely around its existing customers may bring about a variety of threats. For example, planning of goods and services according to the requirements of existing clients may result in the market’s losing its appeal for potential customers. This in turn, may bring about ever rising demands among existing clients of the service. Another threat is that cruise tourists are consumers generally in search of product diversity, according to whose particular needs and expectations, various goods and services in the industry have been adjusted. In the event that these consumers turn to other holiday alternatives, the existing arrangements in services are way behind being capable of meeting the needs of potential customers (Park, 2006:4; İnan et al., 2011:487-497). Therefore, despite these threats, cruise enterprises should turn to different nationalities and demographic characteristics, and, when doing this and dividing market into segments, should correctly analyze the reasons underlying customers’ choice of cruise tourism, their needs and expectations, perceptions of service and behavioral intentions based on scientific data and develop marketing policies and strategies, accordingly.

A review of the literature on this subject reveals that various studies were performed on cruise tourism. While Dwyer and Forsyth (1998), for instance, considered the subject from an economic perspective, Veronneau and Roy (2009) examined cruise tourism for the part of supply chain management. Among the research exploring the matter from the perspective of behaviors of cruise tourists, Douglas et al. (2010) identified a significant relation to exist between brand loyalty and behavioral intentions, in a research they performed. In a research conducted by Andriotis and Agiomirgianakis, cruise tourists were found to lay preference on this modality of tourism, rather for discovering new destinations and new cultures and for getting away from the land, which presented the core of problems for them.

According to Juan and Chen’s research (2011), it was found that ‘service quality’ was important as a determinant not only of participation in enjoying food and beverages but also of use of ‘leisure facilities’, ‘activities and entertainment’, ‘service facilities’ and ‘on-shore tours’. The category with the highest satisfaction was ‘on-shore tours’. In addition, the test results shows that Taiwan cruise tourist overall satisfaction statistically significantly and positively influences re-purchase intentions.

According to Petrick (2004b), quality, value and satisfaction have direct impact on repurchase intention while quality has indirect effect on repurchase intention via the mediators of satisfaction and value.

Furthermore, according to Qu and Ping 's research results (1999) ; Hong Kong cruise tourists reported high satisfaction with 'food and beverage facilities' and 'staff performance' but they were dissatisfied with 'attractiveness, variety and organization of entertainment', 'sport/fitness, shopping and child care facilities'. Also, Qu and Ping (1999) found that 'accommodation', 'food and beverages' and 'entertainment' quality were the main determinants of tourist repeat purchase intentions.

In another research conducted in Korea, it was noted that only 5% of respondents participating in the research have experienced holiday on board a cruise ship and there was a high potential in Korea, who would like to benefit from the merits of cruise tourism (Hur and Adler, 2011). In a further research conducted in the United States with a view to determine such future intentions of consumers taking tours on ships as repurchasing the same product or recommending the product to others, it was proved that evaluation of vacancy or holiday as fun had directly and indirectly comparative effect on possible behavioral intentions of travelers on ships, through their general levels of satisfaction (Duman, 2003:160-178).

Moreover, Duman and Mattila (2005) examined the behavioral intentions of cruise tourists, and measured the degree of impact of a select of emotional factors on perceived values and satisfaction. Kwornik (2008) investigated the impact of the cruise and the ship on passengers' emotions and conception of service and their behaviors on board. Apart from these, Marti (1991), Hobson (1993), Petrick and Sirakaya (2004) and Petrick (2005) discussed cruise tourism from the perspective of market segmentation, while Cessfort and Dingwall (1994), Teye and Leclerc (1998) and Petrick (2003) explored the phenomenon, for the aspects of perceived value and satisfaction.

Objective of the Research

The purpose of this paper has shown as below:

- To determine the items that identifying the perceived service quality in cruise tourism,
- To identify whether these items have any effects on intention for re-purchase and recommendation and general levels of satisfaction, and
- To demonstrate whether a relation exists between the general level of satisfaction with intentions for re-purchase and recommendation.

The goal of this study is to provide perspective to managers and companies related with cruise shipping, travel agencies and tour operators and particularly define this sector as their target market and to provide guidance for further researches to be conducted in future. Furthermore, it is estimated that this paper would contribute to the literature as not only for

identifying whether service quality perceptions of customers have any statistically remarkable effect on their behavioral intentions and general satisfaction levels, but also for verifying whether or not there is a statistically remarkable relationship between the behavioral intentions and general satisfaction levels of customers.

Methodology

The qualitative research method has been used in this study by collecting data via survey in order to achieve the main objective. The questionnaire was comprised of three parts. The first section of survey includes respondents' demographic characteristics. The survey's second part includes SERVQUAL scale variables developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, Valarie and Berry between 1983 and 1990 (Parasuraman et al., 1985; Parasuraman et al., 1988; Zeithaml et al., 1990). Besides, the scale has been reorganized according to cruise services, with particular reference to the fact that service quality dimensions may vary across different service sectors, wherefore, the expressions included in the scale should be readjusted according to each sector, as suggested by a research performed by Carman (1990) on different service enterprises, making use of the SERVQUAL scale. Moreover, it made use of researches reported as performed, in literature on this area, when adapting the survey to the particular field of cruise tourism (Duman and Mattila, 2005; Park, 2006; Andriotis and Agiomirgianakis, 2010; Juan and Chen, 2011; İnan et al., 2011). The third and last section of the survey consists of questions incorporating variables for determining the "intention for re-purchase", "intention for recommending" and "general level of satisfaction" parameters.

Turkish cruise tourists purchasing holiday trips on cruise ships from MSC cruise ship enterprise constitute the universe of this research. The research was conducted on the maritime vessel Divina, owned and operated by MSC Cruise Ship Enterprise, to carry out regular journeys between Izmir, Istanbul and Adriatic ports. The vessel has a full length of 330 meters and a carrying capacity of 4300 passengers. The MSC enterprise reserves average 300 seats for Turkish customers, for each voyage.

The enterprise's preliminary consent was sought and obtained for the conduct of the research, and the researcher joined the journey taking place between August 1st and 8th of 2012, for the purpose. The number of the Turkish passengers on board the cruise ship when it set sail for this journey was 338. A full headcount was attempted made as part of the research, however, questionnaires were given and survey administered on 206 Turkish customers of the ship, due to time limitations. The survey administration

process took place one day before the ship arrived at its pre-designated destinations in Izmir and Istanbul. The respondents were selected according to the convenience sampling method and non-random sampling was made.

During the research, survey questionnaires were drawn up based on a review of the researches hitherto performed in literature, on perceived service quality and cruise tourism, in addition to the use of SERVQUAL scale. A preliminary test was

administered on 18 Turkish cruise tourists who have joined a journey on board a cruise ship before, to test if there were hard-to-answer questions therein, and necessary revisions made according to the feedback supplied.

The respondents' data were evaluated by using the SPSS 15.0 software package. In order to analyze the factors that show the perceived service quality "factor analysis" was performed. Moreover, the regression analysis was used for testing H_1 , H_2 and H_3 . In order to verify H_4 correlation analysis was used.

Problem of the Research

This paper tried to answer below questions:

1. Which factors identify the service quality perception by Turkish cruise tourists, in cruise tourism?
2. Do these perceived service quality factors have any impact on "intention for re-purchase"?
3. Do these perceived service quality factors have any impact on "intention for recommending the service"?
4. Do these perceived service quality factors have any impact on "general level of satisfaction" of customers?
5. Does a relation exist between the general level of satisfaction with intentions for re-purchase and recommendation?

Model of the Research

While efforts were pursued to determine whether the factors forming up the service quality perception of Turkish cruise tourists have any impacts on their intention for re-purchase and recommending the service and general levels of satisfaction, and, attempts were made towards determining whether a statistically significant relationship exists between general level of satisfaction and behavioral intentions.

Hypotheses of the Research

The following hypotheses were developed to test and verify the objectives of this research:

H₁: The perceived service quality factors do have a statistically significant and positive impact on “general level of satisfaction” of tourists.

H₂: The perceived service quality factors do have a statistically significant and positive impact on “intention of re-purchase” of tourists.

H₃: The perceived service quality factors do have a statistically significant and positive impact on “intention of recommending the service or enterprise” of tourists.

H₄: There is a statistically significant and directly proportional relationship between general satisfaction level and behavioral intentions.

Findings

Demographical Characteristics of Answerers of the Survey

Of the 206 Turkish cruise tourists who have responded the survey questionnaire, 92(44, 7%) were female and 114(55, 3%), male. 158(76,7%) respondents were married, while 48 (23,3%) were single. As regards the ages, 18(8, 7%) respondents were in the age grouping of 26 to 35, 56(27, 2%) were in the age range of 36 to 45, 78(37, 9%) were in the age range of 46 to 55 and 54(26, 2%) respondents were at or above the age of 56.

As regards the level of income, 18(8,7%) respondents were in the income level group of Euro1000 to 2000, 44(21,4%) were in the income level group of Euro2001 to 3000, 50(24,3%) were in the income level group of Euro3001 to 4000, 34(16,5%) were in the income level group of 4001 to 5000, 16 (7,8%) were in the income level group of Euro5001 to 6000, 16 (7,8%) were in the income level group of Euro6001 to 7000, 14 (%6,8) were in the income level group of Euro7001 to 8000, eight (3,9%) were in the income level group of Euro8001 to 9000 and six (2.9%) were income level group of above9001 based on feedback supplied by the respondents.

As regards the level of education, eight (%3,9) respondents were found to be graduates of elementary schools, 20(%9,7) were graduates of high schools, 24 were graduates of associate degree schools, 116(%56,3) were graduates of colleges and universities and 38(%18,4) were graduates of institutions of higher education.

Factors of Service Quality as Perceived by Turkish Cruise Tourists

The respondents were asked to express their level of agreement with 29 statements, to determine the factors of Service Quality as Perceived by Turkish Cruise Tourists. Then a factor analysis was performed, with the dual purpose of gathering these variables in a less number of variables and identifying the factors of perceived service quality. The results have shown in Annex 1. During performance of factor analysis for identifying the factors forming up the perceived service quality in cruise tourism, the perceived service quality was explained with 10 factors with a total variance of 72, 10%. These factors were named as “quality and variety of food and beverages”, “accessibility”, “entertainment”, “physical conditions”, “outfit and approach of Staff members”, “eagerness”, “land tours organization”, “empathy”, “information” and “navigation safety”.

Review of Answers Provided To Variables of Intention for Re-Purchase and Recommendation and General Level of Satisfaction

Below provided are answers provided by Turkish cruise tourists to variables concerning their general satisfaction levels and intentions of re-purchase and recommendation.

Table 1.General Satisfaction and Intentions

Variables	Definitely Disagree		Disagree		Neither Agree Nor Disagree		Agree		Definitely Agree		Mean	Std. Dev.
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
General Satisfaction	-	-	2	1,0	3	18,	9	45,	7	35,	4,145	0,744
Re-Purchase	-	-	6	2,9	4	20,	7	35,	8	41,	4,155	0,846
Recommendation	-	-	8	3,9	3	15,	8	40,	8	39,	4,165	0,827

A review of Table 1 suggests that a vast majority of Turkish cruise tourists responding the questionnaire are satisfied with the services provided. Approximately 75% of the respondents wish to join a journey on a cruise ship again. Around 80%, on the other hand, expressed that they would recommend others to take holiday trips on cruise ships.

Impact of Perceived Service Quality Factors on “General Level of Satisfaction” of Customers

A regression analysis was implemented to determine whether perceived service quality factors on “general level of satisfaction” of tourists as obtained and named through the factor analysis has any impact on “general satisfaction level”. According to the model summary of the regression analysis, the 10 service quality perception factors as identified at the end of the factor analysis explains 52.2% of the rate of change in the “intention for re-purchase”, which is a dependent variable. Furthermore, the relationship between variables is significant at a confidence level of 0.05, according to the results of variance analysis performed.

The table of regression analysis coefficients for the impact of perceived service quality factors on “general level of satisfaction” of customers is as follows:

Table 2.The Impact of Perceived Service Quality Factors on “General Level of Satisfaction”

Factors	B	Standard Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	4,146	,037		112,748	,000
Quality and Variety of Food and Beverages	,299	,037	,401	8,102	,000
Accessibility	,165	,037	,221	4,468	,000
Entertainment	,232	,037	,312	6,306	,000
Physical Conditions	,160	,037	,215	4,352	,000
Outfit and Approach of Staff Members	,052	,037	,070	1,413	,159
Eagerness	,142	,037	,191	3,854	,000
Land Tours Organization	,054	,037	,072	1,461	,146
Empathy	,189	,037	,253	5,115	,000
Information	,156	,037	,209	4,222	,000
Navigation Safety	,088	,037	,118	2,390	,018

According to Table 2, it is apparent that quality and variety of food and beverages, accessibility, entertainment, physical conditions, eagerness, empathy, information and navigation safety components of the perceived service quality factors have a statistically significant impact on general satisfaction levels of customers, within a confidence interval of 95%. Based on this result, the hypothesis given in H_1 is acceptable.

Impact of Perceived Service Quality Factors on “Intention for Re-Purchase of Service” of Customers

A regression analysis was implemented to determine whether perceived service quality factors as obtained and named through the factor analysis has any impact on “intention for re-purchase” of customers”. According to the summarized results of the regression analysis model, the ten service quality perception factors as identified at the end of the factor analysis explains 46.1% of the rate of change in the “intention for re-purchase”, which is a dependent variable. Furthermore, the relationship between variables are significant at a confidence level of 0.05, according to the results of variance analysis performed (Model Summary R: 0,679; R^2 :0,461; ANOVA F: 16,665; Sig.:0, 00). The table of regression analysis coefficients for the impact of perceived service quality factors on “intention for re-purchase” of customers is as follows:

Table 3.The Impact of Perceived Service Quality Factors on “Intention for Re-Purchase” of Customers

Factors	B	Standart Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	4,155	,044		93,537	,000
Quality and Variety of Food and Beverages	,276	,045	,326	6,204	,000
Accessibility	,217	,045	,256	4,872	,000
Entertainment	,318	,045	,376	7,150	,000
Physical Conditions	,149	,045	,176	3,344	,001
Outfit and Approach of Staff Members	,086	,045	,101	1,921	,056
Eagerness	,149	,045	,176	3,347	,001
Land Tours Organization	,016	,045	,019	,361	,718
Empathy	,201	,045	,238	4,523	,000
Information	,112	,045	,132	2,507	,013
Navigation Safety	,027	,045	,032	,600	,549

According to Table 3, it is apparent that quality and variety of food and beverages, accessibility, entertainment, physical conditions, eagerness, empathy and information components of the perceived service quality factors have a statistically significant impact on intention for re-purchase of customers, within a confidence interval of 95%. Based on this result, the hypothesis given in H_2 is acceptable.

Impact of Perceived Service Quality Factors on “Intention for Recommending the Service” of Customers

A regression analysis was implemented to determine whether perceived service quality factors as obtained and named through the factor analysis has any impact on customer’s “intention for recommending the service”. According to the

summarized results of the regression analysis model, the ten service quality perception factors as identified at the end of the factor analysis explains 36.1% of the rate of change in the “intention for recommending the service”, which is a dependent variable. Furthermore, the relationship between variables is significant at a confidence level of 0.05, according to the results of variance analysis performed (Model Summary R: 0,601; R²:0,361; ANOVA F: 11,028; Sig.:0, 00). The table of regression analysis coefficients for the impact of perceived service quality factors on “intention for recommending the service” of customers, is as follows:

Table 4.The Impact of Perceived Service Quality Factors on “Intention for Recommending the Service” of Customers

Factors	B	Standard Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	4,165	,047		88,154	,000
Quality and Variety of Food and Beverages	,301	,047	,364	6,354	,000
Accessibility	,075	,047	,091	1,588	,114
Entertainment	,219	,047	,265	4,628	,000
Physical Conditions	,167	,047	,202	3,523	,001
Outfit and Approach of Staff Members	,077	,047	,093	1,629	,105
Eagerness	,149	,047	,180	3,139	,002
Land Tours Organization	,015	,047	,018	,319	,750
Empathy	,194	,047	,234	4,095	,000
Information	,097	,047	,117	2,041	,043
Navigation Safety	,005	,047	,006	,109	,913

According to Table 4, it is apparent that Quality and Variety of Food and Beverages, accessibility, entertainment, physical conditions, eagerness, empathy and information components of the perceived service quality factors have a statistically significant impact on intention for recommending the service of customers, within a confidence interval of 95%.Based on this result, the hypothesis given in H₃ is acceptable.

Analysis of the Relationship between General Satisfaction Level and Intentions for Re-Purchase of and Recommending the Service

A correlation analysis was performed to determine whether a statistically significant relationship exists between the general satisfaction levels and intention for re-purchase and recommendation of the service and the results shown in the table below were obtained.

Table 5. Relationship between General Satisfaction Level and Behavioral Intentions

		Re-Purchase	Recommendation
Pearson Correlation	General Satisfaction	Correlation	,877(**)
		Sig. (2-yönlü)	,000
		Number Of Respondents	206

A review of Table 5 reveals that there is a statistically significant and directly proportional relationship between general satisfaction level and behavioral intentions. Based on this resultant finding, it can be concluded that the intention for re-purchase of and recommending the service by Turkish cruise tourists will tend to rise in line with an increase in their levels of satisfaction for services being provided. Based on this result, the hypothesis given in H₄ is acceptable.

Conclusion and Discussion

The cruise ship industry has been increasing in Turkey. Nowadays most of Turkish people want to make their holidays in cruise ships. So, Turkey has started to be new target market for the cruise ship companies. This research was conducted to determine the impacts of the service quality perceptions of Turkish cruise tourists on their general levels of satisfaction and behavioral intentions. In this research, factors of

service quality perception of Turkish cruise tourists were identified in a count of ten. One of the factors we defined as, “quality and variety of foodstuffs and beverages”. It explains the variety and quality of food and beverage products served at buffets and main restaurant compartments of the cruise ship. The result of the analysis our research shows that “quality and variety of food and beverages” have a positive effect on the general satisfaction levels and intentions for re-

purchase and for recommending the service of Turkish cruise tourists.

“Eagerness” stands for treating customers so as to make them feel self-worthy. The results obtained at the end of analyses show that there is a statistically significant and directly proportional impact of this factor on both general satisfaction level and behavioral intentions. Services offered within the cruise ship in a sincere and heartfelt manner will help Turkish tourists feel valued and will contribute much to their general satisfaction levels and intentions to choose and recommend to others holidays on cruise ships.

Through the analyses, the physical conditions of the cruise ships were found to also have a positive effect on each of the behavioral intentions and satisfaction level. This finding suggests that cleanliness and hygienic conditions of cruise’s cabins, swimming pools, main deck, saloons, walking areas, other common areas and restaurants are important for Turkish cruise tourists. According to the results of the research, “entertainment” comes out to be another factor determined to have impacts on the three variables consisting of “intention for re-purchase”, “intention for recommending” and “general satisfaction level”. The “entertainment” factor stands for the level of professionalism attained, and the quality of dance shows, theatrical and musical performances staged by the animation team of the cruise ship, in addition to their communication skills with the customers and the level of joy and entertainment they provide to them. The resultant findings of the research affirm that the quality and variety of entertainment activities staged or performed on board the cruise ship have positive impact on satisfaction levels of the Turkish cruise tourists.

Furthermore, it appears that also “empathy” factor has a positive effect on both the general satisfaction levels and intentions for re-purchase and recommending the service among Turkish cruise tourists. Empathy means, for both executives and workers of the cruise enterprises, the ability to feel what cruise tourists feel and become familiar with the various needs and requests of them, accordingly, through intuition. Perception of cruise ship executives and workers of the various problems and troubles encountered by Turkish cruise tourists on both technical areas and social matters and accordingly their treating and acting upon the same as if their own and subsequently bringing a pleasant solution will increase the loyalty in and satisfaction of Turkish tourists against the enterprise and the services it offers.

The “information” factor covers information on the timing and manner in which the services are to be delivered, with suitably prior warnings on any potential delays or extraordinary circumstances.

According to the resultant findings of the research, the “information factor” was determined to have positive effect on “general satisfaction level” and behavioral intentions. At this end, it can be said that it would be important to share such information as prompt notices of the times and places of daily entertainment activities and short, suitably prior notices of delays in scheduled times of arrival at a given destination or port of disembarkation, with tourists.

“Accessibility” is the degree and extent of ability of cruise tourists to establish contact with ship’s management and crew whenever they feel the need to convey their needs, requests and grievances about any problems or odds they would be facing throughout the journey. As a result of the analyses performed, “accessibility” factor was found to positive effect on general satisfaction level and intention for repeated preference. Based on this finding, it can be concluded that accessibility is a factor influential on levels of satisfaction among Turkish cruise tourists for services provided and their recommending them to others. The “navigation safety” factor expresses the safe and sound navigation of the ship all along its route, throughout the journey. According to the resultant findings of the research, the “navigation safety” factor was determined to have a statistically significant impact on “general satisfaction level” variable. Moving on this, the level of safety provided in the cruise ship for lives and personal possessions of passengers is an influential factor for Turkish cruise tourists.

Among the other factors, “the outfit and approach of staff members” means kind and genial behaviors shown by decently uniformed members of staff. The “land tours organizations” on the other hand, indicates information and arrangements made for cultural tours to be implemented to destinations.

This research establishes links between certain theories and approaches, for making a theoretical contribution. The first of these is that the perceived service quality factors do have a statistically significant and directly proportional impact on general satisfaction levels and behavioral intentions of tourists. According to these results it is seen that there are similarities between our research and some researches in literature. Qu and Ping (1999) found that ‘accommodation’, ‘food and beverages’ and ‘entertainment’ quality were the main determinants of tourist repeat purchase intentions. In other example, it was demonstrated that consideration of holiday or vacancy as fun had both a directly and indirectly proportional impact on prospective behavioral intentions of travelers taking tours on ships, through their general satisfaction levels (Duman, 2003:160-178). In addition, Petrick (2004b) tested three competing models for predicting behavioral intentions and found that although all three factors (quality, value and satisfaction) directly influence repurchase intention, quality indirectly affects

repurchase intention via the mediators of satisfaction and value.

A statistically significant and directly proportional relationship between general satisfaction level and behavioral intentions was found. These findings show similarities with the result of a research that Juan and Chen conducted on tourists from Taiwan, in 2011. According to Juan and Chen's research (2011), the test results suggested that Taiwan cruise tourist overall satisfaction statistically significantly and positively influences re-purchase intentions. In conclusion, cruise enterprises that are want to choose Turkish cruise tourists as a one of the target market for their company are advised to develop and improve strategies and policies for structuring of their service quality and tourist relations, having due regard to the resultant findings of this research.

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Annex 1: Factors of Service Quality as Perceived by Turkish Cruise Tourists

Statements	Factors									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Factor 1: Quality and Variety of Food and Beverages										
Varieties of Buffet Foodstuffs and Dishes	,835									
Quality of Buffet Foodstuffs and Dishes	,714									
Variety of Beverages	,650									
Quality of Beverages	,620									
Variety of main restaurant dishes	,573									
Quality of main restaurant dishes	,552									
Factor 2:Accessibility										
Accessibility of a responsible person when a problem is encountered		,855								
Ability to communicate with the front office		,787								
Communication of problems to higher management		,541								
Factor 3: Entertainment										
Musicians and Musical Performers			,789							
Communication Skills and Professionalism of Entertainment Team			,779							
Dance Shows			,618							
Theatrical Performances			,412							
Factor 4:Physical Conditions										
Cleanliness and hygiene of cabins				,859						
Cleanliness and hygiene of pools and other common areas				,496						
Cleanliness and hygiene of Restaurants				,481						
Cleanliness of the main deck				,459						
Factor 5:Outfit and Approach of Staff Members										
Outfit of Staff Members					,814					
Politeness and courtesy of Staff Members					,661					
Geniality of Staff Members					,499					
Factor 6:Eagerness										
Staff Members' Desire to Serve						,802				
Treating Customers so as to make them feel Self-Worthy						,763				
Factor 7:Land Tours Organization										
Information and guidance on land tours							,753			
Land Tour organization							,603			
Factor 8:Empathy										
Intuitive knowledge of the requests and needs of customers								,752		
To perceive the problems of passengers as if one's own and act accordingly								,518		
Factor 9:Information										
Information on services to be provided and daily schedule									,758	
Information on possible irregularities									,686	
Factor 10:Navigation Safety										,773
<i>KMO: 0,73 (%73) ; Barlett test; Approx. Chi-Square:2653,588; Sig 0,00); Croanbach Alpha: 0,8731</i>										